

PREDICTING DIABETIC RETINOPATHY USING MACHINE LEARNING**Narayanan C*, Nithya M**, Srinithi P**, Supraja R** & Suruthi M****

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Abstract:

Diabetic retinopathy (DR) is an eye disease caused by the complication of diabetes and we should detect it early for effective treatment. As diabetes progresses, the vision of a patient may start to deteriorate and lead to diabetic retinopathy. As a result, two groups were identified, namely non-proliferative diabetic retinopathy (NPDR) and proliferative diabetic retinopathy (PDR). The amount of the disease spread in the retina can be identified by extracting the features of the retina.

Here this paper proposed Multi Level SVM classifier for better results that's comparatively better than SVM. It provides a better result compared to the existing system using Multilevel support vector machine increase the quality of an image give higher accuracy of retinal damaged place it helps detecting the diabetic retinopathy affected range in retina.

Key Words: Diabetic Retinopathy, NPDR, PDR, Multilevel Support Vector Machine.

Introduction:

Diabetic Retinopathy (DR) is an eye disease that can lead to partial or even complete loss of visual capacity, if left undiagnosed at the initial stage. Retinal lesions associated with diabetes are used to evaluate different stages and the severity of this disease. Micro aneurysms are among the earliest signs of diabetic retinopathy they arise due to high sugar levels in the blood. According to WHO (World Health Organisation) there will be 79 million people with diabetes by 2030, making the India Diabetic capital of the world. Among the patients below the age of 30 years, when first diagnosed with diabetes, the prevalence of retinopathy is 17% during the first 5 years.

This increases to 97% after 15 years of diabetes. Amongst the patients above the age of 30 years, 20% have showed signs of retinopathy immediately after diagnosed and this increased to 78% after 15 years of diabetes. The ratio of ophthalmologists to the number of Diabetic patients is very low. Ophthalmologists in India are insufficient to support the growing Diabetic population. India has 1 Ophthalmologists per 1,00,000 patients and this ratio is even smaller for rural settings.

Medical imaging allows scientists and physicians to understand potential life-saving information using less invasive techniques. This automated algorithm indicates places in the image that require extra attention from the physician because they could be abnormal. These technologies are called Computer Aided Diagnosis (CAD). This paper describes components of an automatic system that can aid in the detection of diabetic retinopathy. As the number of diabetes affected people is increasing worldwide, the need for automated detection methods of diabetic retinopathy will increase as well. To automatically detect diabetic retinopathy, a computer has to interpret and analyze digital images of the retina. This paper predicts the diabetic retinopathy before the early stage.

Existing System:

The paper is method for automatic detection of micro aneurysms are the first clinical sign of diabetic retinopathy and they appear small red dots on retinal images. The number of micro aneurysms is used to indicate the severity of the disease. Early micro aneurysm detection can help reduce the incidence of blindness. As the number of diabetes affected people is increasing worldwide, the need for automated detection methods of diabetic retinopathy will increase as well. To automatically detect diabetic retinopathy, a computer has to interpret images of the retina.

Draw Back:

- Edge detection problem.
- The detection output diabetic not accuracy.

Methodology:

This paper proposed a system to determine the probability that each common type of pathology is present in a given macular cross-section from a known anatomical Position. The objective of proposed system is to diagnosis of multiple macular pathologies in retinal images. The goal is to identify the presence of normal macula and each of three types of macular pathologies, namely, macular hole, cyst detection, denoising decrypting of images and age-related macular degeneration. We use normalization technique for smoothing the input image and morphological and curve filling techniques for segmentation Features are extracted using GLCM and PCA algorithm Our representation operates at multiple spatial scales and granularities, leading to robust performance. We use support vector machine classifiers to identify the presence of normal macula and each of the three pathologies. To further discriminate sub-types within a pathology, we also build a classifier to differentiate full-thickness holes from pseudo-holes within the macular hole category.

Block Diagram:

Hardware Description:

A personal computer (PC) is any general-purpose computer whose size, capabilities, and original sales price make it useful for individuals, and which is intended to be operated directly by an end-user with no intervening computer operator. A computer user will apply application software to carry out a specific task. System software supports applications and provides common services such as memory management, network connectivity, or device drivers; all of which may be used by applications but which are not directly of interest to the end user. A personal computer (PC) is any general-purpose computer

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Software Description:

- MATLAB R2013a
- Coding Language: C
- Tool: Image processing

A. Matlab:

MATLAB (matrix laboratory) is a numerical computing environment and fourth-generation programming language. Developed by Math Works, MATLAB allows matrix manipulations, plotting of functions and data, implementation of algorithms, creation of user interfaces, and interfacing with programs written in other languages, including C, C++, Java, and FORTRAN. Although MATLAB is intended primarily for numerical computing, an optional toolbox uses the MuPAD symbolic engine, allowing access to symbolic computing capabilities. MATLAB is a high-level technical computing language and interactive environment for algorithm development, data visualization, data analysis, and numerical computation. MATLAB can call functions and subroutines written in the C programming language or Fortran. A wrapper function is created allowing MATLAB data types to be passed and returned.

B. Image Processing:

Image processing is a method to convert an image into digital form and perform some operations on it, in order to get an enhanced image or to extract some useful information from it. Usually Image Processing system includes treating images as two dimensional signals while applying already set signal processing methods to them. It is among rapidly growing technologies today, with its applications in various aspects of a business. Image Processing forms core research area within engineering and computer science disciplines too.

- In medical science the problem as well as the data stream is three-dimensional and the effort to solve the problem is mostly combination of both human and machine.
- Medical tasks can often be split into three areas:
- Data operations like filtering, noise removal, and contrast and feature enhancement
- Detection of medical conditions and events
- Qualitative analysis of the lesion or detected events.

C. Support Vector Machine:

Support Vector Machine (SVM) is a supervised machine learning algorithm which can be used for either classification or regression challenges. However, it is mostly used in classification problems. In this algorithm, we plot each data item as a point in n-dimensional space (where n is number of features you have) with the value of each feature being the value of a particular coordinate. Then, we perform classification by finding the hyper-plane that differentiates the two classes very well. This increases the quality but also reduces the performance dramatically. We introduce a generalized fast multilevel framework for regular and weighted SVM and discuss several versions of its algorithmic components that lead to a good trade-off between quality and time.

**Projections for Diabetic Retinopathy
in 2030 and 2050 (in millions)**

Advantages:

- Early Detection: Machine learning models can identify diabetic retinopathy at its early stages when treatment is more effective, thus helping in preventing vision loss.

- Efficiency: Automation of the diagnosis process reduces the workload on healthcare professionals and enables faster analysis of large volumes of retinal images. Helps to reduced processing time and provide automated process.
- Accuracy: Machine learning algorithms can achieve high accuracy levels in diagnosing diabetic retinopathy, sometimes even outperforming human experts..
- MSVM provide better accuracy compared to the SVM process.

Result & Discussion:

Detection of diabetic retinopathy in retinal image is a challenging one .So we predict the method for detection in three stages. One is to remove the impurities from the image. Another one is to extract the features from the image. Features would be really helpful to identify the disease. In retina the abnormal tissue has to be grown in enormous manner than normal tissue which are categorized under an abnormal image. If the retina contain some normal tissue are categorized under normal image. Identifying the location of disease can be done using MSVM classification. The experimental results have shown that this technique is robust in detecting and bounding the abnormal cells in retinal images despite in homogeneity intensity or the complicate shape of the diabetic retinopathy. This paper done the prediction of diabetic retinopathy using machine learning give the result of 5% increases the accuracy compared then the existing system.

R Grade	Retinopathy Level
Level R0	No Retinopathy
Level R1	Background Retinopathy
Level R2	Pre-Proliferative Retinopathy
Level R3A	Active Proliferative Retinopathy
Level R3S	Stable Treated Proliferative Retinopathy
P1	Evidence Of Laser Photocoagulation
U	Unassessable

Conclusion:

In this article, we looked at the machine learning algorithm, Support Vector Machine in detail. We discussed its concept of working, process of implementation in python, the tricks to make the model efficient by tuning its parameters, Pros and Cons, and finally a problem to solve. MSVM provide a better accuracy level compared to the SVM this process is done by the machine learning technique. We using the C language code for predicting the diabetic retinopathy it helps to pre-detecting and analysis the amount of disease spread in the eye is identified. There are a number of things that can be improved upon and added to the system. Improve the filtering process for an image and the feature extraction of retinal tissues are to be collected for identifying the severity level of a disease. Neural networks have shown great promise in this area, and would likely be the main focus for future work. It can analyse the classification part in accurate manner .This paper concluded that the experiment provide the better result so the disease is predicted before the complicated stage.

Limitations:

- While GLCM and PCA are powerful techniques for feature extraction, they may not capture all relevant information present in the retinal images. There could be other texture or shape features that are important for accurate diagnosis but are not effectively encoded by the chosen methods.
- One of the limitations of the usage of machine learning with medical field faces is the size of the datasets needed to train the ML systems, as ML is required large amount of data.
- The gap that needed to be covered is the existence of systems that could determine the five DR stages with high accuracy as well as detecting DR lesions. This point could be considered as the current challenge for researchers for further investigations.

Future Work:

In future we would like to improve the accuracy of the system in detecting the Diabetic Retinopathy defect so that the results are more accurate and clear. Also, we would like to make the whole tool accessible as a web or mobile application so that it provides a much more user friendly and integrated platform.

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